

Sovereignty's Missing Moral Imperative

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...this generation must persevere in the effort necessary to add its stone to the building that rises to the greater good of humanity.

N. Politis, *La Justice Internationale*, 1924*

Introductory Comments

1. The following paper claims that the theoretical construct of sovereignty was not only expropriated by the Christian religion out of ancient religious beliefs – shared with them by both Jewish and Muslim traditions – but, perhaps more importantly for modern policy considerations, that it always insisted on a positive moral imperative being placed on the person or body executing it in practice. Further below I will discuss some traditional understandings of theoretical sovereignty and comment on how they interact with my claim. Before beginning, though, I offer a hermeneutical warning to the reader – and using this derivative of the word ‘hermeneutic,’ that thunderous and often misused word, may be permitted here since sovereignty itself is a word that was taken directly from religious *writings* and belief.¹ This author recognizes the difficulty of taking on a historical idea which inures as much controversy as sovereignty – not least because of the highly charged emotional reactions which inure for invested bureaucrats, politicians, lawyers, and even academics who treasure a particular historical interpretation of its evolution and/or practice. It may appear, at times, that these stakeholders will do anything in their power to protect what they see as “their” Western history and interpretation of it. Paul Valéry sternly rebuked this kind of ideological drunkenness writing:

History is the most dangerous product which the chemistry of the mind has concocted. Its properties are well known. It produces dreams and drunkenness. It fills people with false memories, exaggerates their reactions, exacerbates old grievances, torments them in their repose, and encourages either a delirium of grandeur or a delusion of persecution. It makes whole nations bitter, arrogant, insufferable, and vainglorious.²

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¹ *Vide infra*

² Paul Valéry, *Regards sur le Monde Actuel & autres essais*, nouvelle édition revue et augmentée (Paris: Librairie Gallimard, 1945), 43. L’Histoire est le produit le plus dangereux que la chimie de L’intellect ait élaboré. Ses propriétés sont bien connues. Il fait rêver, il enivre les peuples, leur engendre de faux souvenirs, exagère leurs réflexes, entretient leurs vieilles plaies, les tourmente dans leur repos, les conduit au délire des grandeurs ou à celui de la persécution, et rend les nations amères, superbes, insupportables et vaines. English translation: History is the most dangerous product which the chemistry of the mind has concocted. Its properties are well known. It produces dreams and drunkenness. It fills people with false memories, exaggerates their reactions, exacerbates old grievances, torments them in their repose, and encourages either a delirium of grandeur or a delusion of persecution. It makes whole nations bitter, arrogant (sic), insufferable, and vainglorious. Paul Valéry, *Regards sur le Monde Actuel* (Paris, 1949), p. 43, as in David Hackett Fischer, *Historians’ Fallacies: Towards a Logic of Historical Thought* (New York: Harper Torchbooks, 1970), 307-308.

Valéry goes on to note that “History justifies what we want. She teaches nothing rigorously, because it contains everything, and gives examples of everything.”³ Yet there is the rub, because history – as if it was not evidentially problematic enough – comes with examples which suit diverse interpretations of many historical questions. If, as Valéry writes, history is not capable of being rigorous, perhaps we can at least hope that those in the historical theory-making business ought to be. To this end, the bottom line in sovereignty theorizing ought to take account of two important facts: first, that it is the practioners, policy makers, and readers/citizens⁴ who are the affective judges and juries on what theory be adopted and put into practice; second, and more importantly, that it will ultimately be citizens within nation states who are affected most pointedly by these theories in praxis. With this in mind, it should then be reasonable to insist that historical processes and personages, at least what we can infer about them from the source documents, should not lead us inexorably to any kind of *fait accompli* about what sovereignty has to mean.

2. Documented history, for better or worse, is a written legacy left to everyone, and only a confused mind would insist otherwise. While it is true that no one person has any more claim to a history – the *source documents* of history – than anyone else, it should matter to us how an idea like sovereignty is *used* and how it gets applied – especially in our world full of diverse nations, nationalities, and the seemingly perennial and concomitant conflict which affects some of them. Empirical sovereignty, or the practice of it, involves life and death issues for citizens who are affected by the decisions of governing bodies: whether they are local, national, or international. Does anyone doubt that General Shwe’s practice of internal sovereignty during the Cyclone Nargis crisis had an impact on Burmese citizens that was of a life and death nature? Of course, they tragically *were* of that nature. But where does that leave theories on sovereignty?

3. Sovereignty *theory* only becomes a life and death issue when it crosses the Rubicon into application. In this sense, sovereignty theory is very important. If so, we must set aside any self-appointed guardians of the word, often heady on the fumes of their smoldering structural fictions, and insure that the explanations and definitions that are given for sovereignty are both equitable and functional. I suggest that it is necessary to take Valéry’s rebuke seriously and by so doing warn ourselves off of any pre-conceived ideas of what sovereignty “needs” to mean. Like the General Semantics school taught us so well, beginning with Alfred Korzybski in 1933, “[t]he map is *not* the territory it represents...;”⁵ and later in the hands of S.I. Hayakawa, “[t]he symbol is NOT the thing

³ Paul Valéry, *Regards sur le Monde Actuel & autres essays*, 1945, 43. [I]’Histoire justifie ce que l’on veut. Elle n’enseigne rigoureusement rien, car elle contient tout, et donne des exemples de tout.

⁴ In the sense that once read, the data will impinge on the cognitive processes of people’s minds as they further construct or de-construct their world views. In other words, non-practioners and non-policy-making types can have a profound effect on the attitudes and beliefs of their fellow citizens.

⁵ Alfred Korzybski, *Science and Sanity: An Introduction to Non-Aristotelian Systems and General Semantics*, fourth ed. (Lakeville, Connecticut: The International Non-Aristotelian Library Publishing Company, 1933; 1958), 58.

symbolized; the word is NOT the thing; the map is NOT the territory it stands for.”⁶ “Sovereignty” is a word; it is not, nor can it be, actual sovereignty. Sovereignty is a symbol for the thing symbolized, not the thing symbolized. What empirical sovereignty *is* for our modern world, what it has *become* in practice, are the many tendrils of state governments, both internally and externally, and their concomitant actions and affects in relation to citizens and other states, respectively. As a theoretical construct, though, sovereignty is more precarious and uncertain.

4. Commentators on sovereignty from Jean Bodin to F.H. Hinsley have given us maps of what they understood sovereignty's territory, if you will, to look like. They are not giving us sovereignty itself, but only ideas which they insist add up to a satisfactory working definition of a theory of sovereignty. Those who analyze the theories of Bodin and Hinsley in their writings, then, are giving us maps of maps about sovereignty. With sovereignty's ever more diversified and uncertain theoretical trajectories, we are abstracting the idea so far from the purposes for which a theory of sovereignty can be justified that it becomes unclear who the actual shareholders are. In the following paper I suggest that unless theoretical sovereignty can be meaningfully connected to its epistemological roots, wherein the citizen's protection and benefit is the body around which all other incidental considerations orbit, that our investigations into its true nature are near meaningless gestures reflecting, rather, what given interests think it ought to be. In other words, if the well being of citizens is not the central focus of sovereignty theories in praxis, nothing should be, and a more appropriate word for what passes as sovereignty should replace it.

⁶ S.I. Hayakawa, *Language in Thought and Action* (New York: Harcourt, Brace and Company, 1941; 1949), 31. Hayakawa takes “the map is not the territory” directly from the first person to bring General Semantics into the main stream of academia, Alfred Korzybski: Alfred Korzybski, *Science and Sanity: An Introduction to Non-Aristotelian Systems and General Semantics*, fourth ed. (Lakeville, Connecticut: The International Non-Aristotelian Library Publishing Company, 1933; 1958). Korzybski, in turn, apparently [p. 247] took the mapping idea from E.T. Bell, *Numerology* (Baltimore: The Williams & Wilkins company, 1933). Another theory which borrows heavily from this comes from sociologist Edward T. Hall, who suggested the idea of Extension Transference (ET) in which an extension is confused with the process intended: Edward T. Hall, *Beyond Culture* (Garden City, New York: Anchor Books, 1977), 28-29. Hall does mention Korzybski and Wendell Johnson and predecessors of his who had a similar idea first and were the founders of semantics.

Some Historically Situated Notions about Sovereignty

O Enlil, the lord who decides destinies, whose commands cannot be altered, who makes my sovereignty magnificent...

King Hammurabi, *Code of Hammurabi* (18th c. B.C.E.)

... περί τε τῆς ἀρχῆς καὶ περὶ τῆς πόλεως, καὶ διὰ μάχης ἐχώρησαν, ἐν ἧ ὁ Ῥώμιος ἀπέθανεν....

Zonaras 7,3. *Dio's Roman History*

5. Let us begin by briefly looking at some historical examples of what sovereignty might have meant in the context of history. Clearly, from this statement of Hammurabi, to have authority and power was something only based on the “decision” of his god. What is interesting is that 3300 years later, Jean Bodin would say essentially the same thing about sovereignty and his God.⁷ What we can say with certainty about this nexus is that although the modern translator of the ancient Akkadian text of Hammurabi puts the word in his mouth, it was not until we reach Bodin that the *word* sovereignty was abstracted from theology and placed at the feet of kings. Notice again, though, how this ancient Babylonian King, who bequeathed history with one of the first known written codes of law, was specific to mention in his code exactly who it was who underwrote the sovereignty, and importantly, for his own legitimacy, who executed it.

6. Almost one millennium after Hammurabi, as indicated above, in the eighth century, we learn from the historian Zonaras that “sovereignty”⁸ or ultimate authority, specifically the question of who should wield such, was the cause of Remus’ death at the hands of his twin brother Romulus.⁹ It seems that in the minds of the two founding brothers of Rome, ultimate authority could not rest in the hands of both and thus it ultimately rested with one. Yet Rome’s history shows that such a monarchical arrangement was unsatisfactory to many, and in time kings were replaced with a republican scheme, which was, itself, subsequently vanquished by an imperial system of governance. I note here, though, that sovereign authority in all these circumstances, devolved as it had on various arrangements of interested parties, never wholly moved beyond the class *and* religious interests which characterized the lives of its executors. In other words, from Hammurabi to Hadrian, and even on past to the Hapsburgs, the only affective benefactor of sovereignty was, at least in theory,¹⁰ the deity. In societies where religion was the fundamental framework of daily

⁷ *Vide infra.*

⁸ ἀρχῆς in the Greek can mean first place, headship, authority, etc. *The Analytical Greek Lexicon* (New York: Harper & Brothers; London: Samuel Bagster and Sons, 1870, 1983), 53.

⁹ ‘[Romulus and Remus disputed] about the sovereignty and the city, and they got into a conflict in which Remus was killed.’ Zonaras 7,3, *Dio's Roman History*, trans. Earnest Cary (London: William Heinemann, 1914), Book I, 17.

¹⁰ Theory, meaning, for instance during the Middle Ages, if a king had to justify his rule the pope and bishops would do so on behalf of God. Theory here obviously cannot refer to theories *on* sovereignty, which did not appear until well after the turn of the first millennium.

life for all classes,¹¹ rulers, for the sake of legitimacy, had to acknowledge that it was the God or 'the gods' who had bequeathed their sovereignty. In this context sovereignty was never aggregately or individually understood as solely attached to either the will or skill of personages, it came from the deity.

Words, Meanings, and Dominion

7. The key question I have asked here is whether "sovereignty", along with its terminological forbears such as authority and dominion, consisted of a moral element alongside its substantive definition of an ability to "rule" over a given body of people and territory. The further back one goes in the history of authority/sovereignty as an idea, the more this moral component seems to show up. I will briefly review some key historical ideas we could fairly associate with sovereignty.

8. The basic idea first arises with the Greek philosophers of the classical period. It then is imported into Roman ideology, then into the Catholic world view, and finally to European political theorists in the Early Modern and Modern period. The theory behind the development of sovereignty as an idea begins, like almost every other idea in Western thinking, with Greece's three foremost philosophers: Socrates (469-399 B.C.E.), Plato (427-347 B.C.E.), and Aristotle (384-322 B.C.E.). For all three, their inquiry in to the best of all possible governance options was consumed with the desire for justifiable and efficient sovereignty, and they blatantly jettisoned the clumsy tyrannies of flawed oligarchy, pure democracy, and all anarchies in favour of a system which represented, if not the peoples wishes, then certainly their best interests. The "right to rule" here also necessitated a "right" rule. Cicero (106-43 B.C.E.), as well, repeated Plato's desire for the best of all possible outcomes in his own *Republic*, and he could reasonably be counted among those who saw things in terms of highest "good" or utility. The ideas of Plato were then co-opted by Saint Augustine (354-450 C.E.) via Cicero's writings into the doctrine of the Catholic Church, and ideas which had begun with the Greeks, such as "just war" and the role of rulers' vis-à-vis the state, were fashioned to fit Augustine's particular Christian world view.¹²

¹¹ Augustine, *Concerning The City of God against the Pagans*, trans. Henry Bettenson (London: Penguin, 1984), 4.11, 149-152; see chapter four of *City of God* generally for similar evidences of the role of gods in the lives of Romans. See also, A.D. Lee, *Traditional Religions, The Cambridge Companion to the Age of Constantine*, ed. Noel Lenski (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2006); Keith Hopkins, *A World Full of Gods: Pagans, Jews and Christians in the Roman Empire* (London: Weidenfeld & Nicolson, 1999); Michael Lipka, *Roman Gods: A Conceptual Approach* (Leiden: Brill, 2009).

¹² See James L. Cook, " "With whom he was in a state of just war...": A Review of the Just War Tradition," *Word & World* 24.1 (2004): 50; Stevenson, William R. Jr. *Christian Love and Just War: Moral Paradox and Political Life in St. Augustine and His Modern Interpreters* (Mercer University Press: Macon, 1987); John Langan, "The Elements of St. Augustine's Just War Theory," *The Ethics of St. Augustine*, ed. William S. Babcock (Scholars Press: Atlanta, 1991); etc.

Socrates and Plato

The safest general characterization of the European philosophical tradition is that it consists of a series of footnotes to Plato.
Alfred North Whitehead, *Process and Reality*

9. I think the most important thing to keep in mind when considering the influence of Plato and Socrates¹³ on the history of political ideas and ideologies is the notion that *true* justice is a state of affairs wherein everyone in the *polis* works at the task which they are most suited to.¹⁴ In his famous dialogue with Glaucon and other interlocutors in Plato's *Republic*, Socrates concludes that each citizen ought to commit themselves to the task in their community which their *character* most suited them for.¹⁵ Socrates espouses this notion primarily because he is trying to lay out a formula for the ideal republic, the ideal state, if you will. Socrates is careful to separate the different characters of people into different tasks for the benefit of the city, for instance giving people with a more rudimentary character the more menial tasks, and those of a higher character the important tasks. In this way, Socrates is really instituting an unveiled system of class whereby order and functionality are the goals. He separates citizens into one of three classes: commercial, auxiliary, and the decision-makers.¹⁶ The citizens in the commercial class do the farming, the trades, and all of the daily work which is required by the needs of any given *polis*. The citizens of the auxiliary are essentially the military class, who guard the city and enforce the rules of the "decision-makers". Lastly, these decision-makers, referred to as 'philosopher kings,' are those of the highest character who make decisions for the rest of the *demos*. According to Socrates, it is only to these latter figures that sovereign rule and the guardianship of state sovereignty could ever be entrusted.

10. For Plato's Socrates, sovereignty, or the power to rule, would, ideally, only rest in the hands of those few who had the character and training to manage it.

There is no end to suffering, Glaucon, for our cities, and none, I suspect, for the human race, unless either philosophers become kings in our cities, or the people who are now called kings and rulers become, in the truest and most complete sense of the word, philosophers – unless there is this amalgamation of political power and philosophy, with all those people whose inclination is to pursue one or other

¹³ Socrates is the main character in most of the dialogues of Plato. Plato was a student of Socrates and scholars have never been able to say with final authority how much of Plato's writings were the ideas of Socrates and which were merely those of Plato from the mouth of Socrates. See, for instance, Gregory Vlastos, *Socrates: Ironist and Moral Philosopher* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1991), 45-80. I refer, in this paper, to the ideas and recommendations of *Socrates*, vis-à-vis Plato, since that is the way Plato presented them, as the ideas of Socrates. Furthermore, both Aristotle and Cicero answer Socrates in their writings, but of course they are answering Socrates *in* Plato, often not even mentioning the latter. I have chosen not to break rank with such an ancient tradition.

¹⁴ Plato, *The Republic*, trans. Tom Griffith, ed. G.R.F. Ferrari, in *Cambridge Texts in the History of Political Thought*, eds. Raymond Geuss and Quentin Skinner (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2000), 4.433a-433b, 127.

¹⁵ Plato, *The Republic*, 2000, 4.433a-433b, 127.

¹⁶ Plato, *The Republic*, 2000, 4.440e-441a, 137.

exclusively being forcibly prevented from doing so. Otherwise there is not the remotest chance of the political arrangements we have described coming about – to the extent that they can – or seeing the light of day.¹⁷

Socrates also understood most of humankind as being under a fundamental deception about what was good for them.¹⁸ It is this fact which gives impetus to his prescriptions for the ideal state, and how that state should be ruled. Importantly for this discussion of sovereignty, the idea of humans as debilitated and misguided beings implies the need for deliberate governance, which ends up coloring every vision of sovereign rule from Aristotle to Hobbes.

11. The implicit inference that might fairly be made about Socrates' teaching is that such weighty political power should only be awarded those citizens who kept the best interests of the state as a whole as their *raison d'être*. The all important consideration for this Greek philosopher was capacity. If men and women were the best candidates to lead, they should be compelled to do so. By this reasoning, state sovereignty would only rest in the hands of those disciplined enough to control the power that was concomitant with their rule. Besides bare efficiency, it is clear that Socrates, as well as Aristotle after him, was aiming his prescriptions so as to cause people to arrive as close to the "good" as they possibly could. Hence, there seems implicit in Socrates' strictures for the capacity to rule, a moral and deeply prescriptive element at its heart. For Socrates, it is not enough that kings or oligarchs, or even citizens, wield the largest share of political power in their states, it is whether that sovereign power is the product of the "good". As to the fountainhead of this notion of "good," like many of the theorists who ended up weighing in on sovereignty after Socrates, he appealed to God.¹⁹

¹⁷ Plato, *The Republic*, 2000, 5.473d-473e, 175.

¹⁸ Plato, *The Republic*, 2000, 7.514a-515a, 220. The classic Cave Metaphor is here apropos, humans in chains in need of a special person to come down and bring them up towards the sunlight of the "good.":

Socrates: 'Picture human beings living in some sort of underground cave dwelling, with an entrance which is long, as wide as the cave, and open to the light. Here they live, from earliest childhood, with their legs and necks in chains, so that they have to stay where they are, looking only ahead of them, prevented by the chains from turning their heads. They have light from a distant fire, which is burning behind them and above them. Between the fire and the prisoners, at a higher level than them, is a path along which you must picture a low wall that has been built, like the screen which hides people when they are giving a puppet show, and above which they make the puppets appear.'

Glaucon: 'Yes, I can picture that,' he said.

S: 'Picture also, along the length of the wall, people carrying all sorts of implements which project above it, and statues of people, and animals made of stone and wood and all kinds of materials. As you'd expect, some of the people carrying the objects are speaking, while others are silent.'

G: A strange picture. And strange prisoners.

¹⁹ Plato, *The Republic*, 2000, 10.597d, 316; 2.379a, 64; 2.379c-379d, 64.

Aristotle

Ἔχει δ' ἀπορίαν τί δεῖ τὸ κύριον εἶναι τῆς πόλεως.
Aristotle, *Politics*

12. As this comment from Aristotle suggests,²⁰ who or what, exactly, should hold the sovereign power over a city or state is not something which was altogether clear, even during his lifetime in the fourth century B.C.E. While Socrates' dialogues with interlocutors sketch sovereignty in an implicit way, Aristotle discusses the subject explicitly. In Aristotle's *Politics*, he engages in a discussion about the various systems of governance then in existence, and makes suggestions as to what might be the most efficient method. The topic of sovereignty comes up a number of times and I will briefly discuss his usage of the word to better clarify where he saw its appropriate locus.

13. The word in Greek which Aristotle uses for sovereignty is κύριον (kurion). The meaning of this Greek word is 'to have power or authority over people'.²¹ So the question Aristotle is really asking is 'who should have authority over the people in a city or state?' In a very fundamental way, Aristotle first comments on sovereignty as something which aims at some good²² and vests in the city or state itself.²³ Yet Aristotle's major contribution to the idea of political authority was to suggest moving beyond the bounds of trained citizenry set by Socrates to suggest that the law should be the foundation upon which ideal governance might rest.

[There is] one conclusion above all others. Rightly constituted laws should be [the final] sovereign; but rulers, whether one or many, should be sovereign in those matters on which law is unable, owing to the difficulty of framing general rules for all contingencies, to make an exact pronouncement. But what rightly constituted laws ought to be is a matter that is not yet clear; and here we are still confronted by the difficulty stated at the end of the previous chapter. Laws must be good or bad, just or

²⁰ Aristotle, *Politics*, trans. H. Rackham, *The Loeb Classical Library*, eds. T.E. Page et. al. (London: William Heinemann, 1950), 3.6.1, 219: "But it is a matter of question what ought to be the sovereign power in the state."

²¹ Henry George Liddell and Robert Scott, compilers, *A Greek-English Lexicon*, rev. Henry Stuart Jones (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1925), 1013.

²² Aristotle, *Politics*, trans. Ernest Barker, rev. R. F. Stalley (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1995), 7.2, 257. The task of a good lawgiver is to see how any city or race of men or society with which he is concerned, may share in a good life and in whatever form of happiness is available to them. See also Aristotle, *Politics*, 7.13, 281. The best constituted city is the city which possesses the greatest possibility of achieving happiness.

²³ Aristotle, *Politics*, trans. Ernest Barker, rev. R. F. Stalley (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1995), Book 1.1, 7. Observation shows us, first, that every city [*polis*] is a species of association, and, secondly, that all associations come into being for the sake of some good – for all men do all their acts with a view to achieving something which is in their view, a good. It is clear therefore that all associations aim at some good, and that the particular association which is the most sovereign of all, and includes all the rest, will pursue this aim most, and will thus be directed to the most sovereign of all goods. This most sovereign and inclusive association is the city [or *polis*], as it is called, or the political association.

unjust in the same way as the constitutions to which they belong. The one clear fact is that laws must be laid down in accordance with constitutions; and if this is the case, it follows that laws which are in accordance with right constitutions must necessarily be just, and laws which are in accordance with perverted constitutions must be unjust.²⁴

When considering the major revolutionary constitutional projects of, for instance, France, England, and the United States, over the last three hundred years, it is remarkable how they all seem to adhere relatively closely to this set of recommendations based on a compromise between laws and ruler which was proposed over two millennia ago. Beginning with the modern period, at the end of the era of religion's dominance over the political and legal affairs of Europe, and coming right into our own day, this idea from Aristotle that law should be cast in accordance with a just constitution and that only in cases wherein the law cannot address matters should a ruler/court be able to intervene, is strikingly familiar to most models of governance now operating in the western world. The question could then be put, though, whether the West has, in adopting the pre-eminence of law, forgotten the notion of good?

Dominion and Sovereignty in Ancient Scriptures

14. The word “sovereignty”, appears in the Jewish Scriptures only seven times, and only in the books of the prophets Daniel and Micah.²⁵ The book of Daniel, appearing just after the age of the aforementioned philosophers and just before the Christian era, cites the Aramaic/Chaldean word which is now translated as sovereignty to be ²⁶טְשִׁיבָהּ which translates “and Dominion of Him” from a passage which reads in English, “his sovereignty is from generation to generation.”²⁷ The root word is ²⁸טָשַׁב and is defined as “to rule, have dominion or power over.”²⁹ Essentially what this means is that the Aramaic/Chaldean translator is treating the idea of “dominion over” as meaning what they believe the English word “sovereignty” to mean. There is one necessary caveat here: it is God who is the holder of the sovereignty. Let us ask ourselves right away here: are today's nation states in any way similar to a supernatural entity of which all religions agree that, by definition, is the only one of whom none greater can be conceived?³⁰ In other words, if God is the holder and sometimes benefactor of this ancient example of

²⁴ Aristotle, *Politics*, 3.11, 111-112.

²⁵ Examples would include Daniel 4.3:

His kingdom is an everlasting kingdom,
and his sovereignty is from generation to generation; and Micah 4.8:
And you, O tower of the flock,
hill of daughter Zion,
to you it shall come,
the former dominion shall come,
the sovereignty of daughter Jerusalem.

²⁶ *The NIV Interlinear Hebrew English Old Testament*, ed. John R. Kohlenberger III, vol. 4 Isaiah – Malachi (Grand Rapids: Zondervan, 1985), 450.

²⁷ See passage at footnote 10.

²⁸ D. Davidson, *The Analytical Hebrew and Chaldee Lexicon* (London: Samuel Bagster and Sons Ltd., 1848; 1972), 719.

²⁹ *Ibid.*

³⁰ I borrow the familiar phraseology from St. Anselm's ‘Ontological Argument’.

“sovereignty”, should we expect nation states to be able to successfully navigate what was originally an attribute of God? If anyone wants to pretend historical continuity with sovereignty’s evolutionary nexus of meanings, they will be faced with the predicament that what we call sovereignty as an idea may be out of the realm of possibility for a state in any event.

15. The Jewish Scriptures, although modern translators have only imposed the word sovereignty on the text minimally, were the basis of early Christian religious doctrine and were also the primary source of written authority for the young religion until at least the late fourth century.³¹ Earlier in that same century, in 325 C.E., was an important event I have written elsewhere about,³² the Constantinian Council of Nicaea. This gathering of regional authority figures, in the persons of the bishops, occasioned perhaps the most important transfer of sovereignty concerning Europe’s future. The Constantinian marriage of the Christian Church and Roman State would set a precedent for political authority which was imitated in Europe right up until, at least, the Peace of Westphalia in 1648. In brief, the Christian Church exchanged the sovereignty of God, an idea which they inherited from the Jewish Religion and Scriptures, for supposed co-regency between the Emperor and God. Here in the fourth century was the Constantinian transfer of sovereignty from the God of the Christian religion to the state. Of course the nexus did not play out in Constantine’s lifetime as completely as it would in later centuries with Popes like Gregory I, et al.³³ Constantine changed the fact that Christ was exclusively and self-admittedly only interested in participating in the sovereign rule of the Kingdom of God³⁴ to a Christ who would now vouchsafe the sovereignty of the Roman Empire. For the rest of Europe’s history, sovereign rule and power would be something associated with both God and the state, and in time the notion of God would be separated out

³¹ I have written in detail on this subject in C.G. Bateman, *Origen's Role in the Formation of the New Testament Canon* (August 3, 2010). Available at SSRN: <http://ssrn.com/abstract=1653073>.

³² C.G. Bateman, “Nicaea and Sovereignty: The Introduction of An Idea about the Beginnings of State Sovereignty,” *International Zeitschrift* 7.2 (October 2011): 32-73.

³³ Richards, Jeffrey, *Consul of God: The Life and Times of Gregory the Great* (London: Routledge & Kegan Paul, 1980), 127. R.A. Markus, *Gregory the Great and His World* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1997), 11. Since the time of Constantine churches had built up extensive land holdings. By the end of the sixth century they were the largest landowners in Italy. In Gregory’s time the Roman Church must have been by far the richest. It had long had registers (*polyptycha*) of its lands and of the income it derived from them, which were kept up to date. Its possessions were concentrated in Sicily and in Campania; but the ‘patrimony (of St Peter)’, as these possessions were collectively known, included lands scattered over Southern Italy (Bruttium-Lucania and Apulia-Calabria), Tuscany, and elsewhere in Italy, Corsica and Sardinia, Dalmatia, Gaul, and North Africa. F.H. Dudden, *Gregory the Great: His Place in History and Thought* (London: Longmans, Green & Co., 1905), i, 296.

³⁴ Ernest Renan, *The Life of Jesus*, trans. Charles E. Wilbour (The Modern Library Publishers: New York, 1927), 159. To whom should we turn, to whom should we trust to establish the kingdom of God? The mind of Jesus on this point never hesitated. That which is highly esteemed among men, is abomination in the sight of God. The founders of the kingdom of God are the simple. Not the rich, not the learned, not priests; but women, common people, the humble, and the young. The great characteristic of the Messiah is, that “the poor have the gospel preached to them” [Matt. 6:5]. The idyllic and gentle nature of Jesus here resumed the superiority. *A great social revolution, in which rank will be overturned, in which all authority in this world will be humiliated, was his dream* [Emphasis mine]. See also pp. 154-155.

completely, so that a state could imagine itself as being sovereign: something originally only thought to be under the jurisdiction and control of God.

16. Sovereignty scholar F.H. Hinsley has likely produced the most enduring recent re-characterization of sovereignty,³⁵ but it departs from earlier ideas in almost every way other than associating the word with coercive power. Hinsley wrote that sovereignty was long understood as being the only unqualified authority within a political system,³⁶ and that it became an idea which people used to either strengthen older forms of legitimation, or they tailored it in new ways on the way to converting their raw authority into power.³⁷ He also poignantly noted that so long as the definition ends with “and no final and absolute authority exists elsewhere,” sovereignty could be satisfactorily defined.³⁸ Hinsley’s apologetic treatise on sovereignty, though, rests on an efficiency axiom that the modern complexity of human society leads to greater government intervention via its sovereign power which in turn makes the state even more complex, notwithstanding criticisms to the contrary.³⁹

17. Some of the burgeoning complexities may have had little to do with human rights, such as the growth of cities and the industrial revolution, but when we look at the transformation of legal instruments and the vast changes in functional political structures in the course of the latter half of the second millennium of the Common Era, we see that the general direction for both these phenomena were towards a greater protection of human and political rights for the people living in these nascent states. From the *Magna Carta* to the Protestant Reformation, and on to the revolutionary wars of the modern period, the orientation of these events was ultimately about the rights of people, however obfuscated the individual events were by the egos of monarchs, popes, and generals.

18. It would seem that any justification on the need for preserving sovereignty based on the complexity arising from Modern and Post-modern societal change will have to insist that such change be consistent and continual, where necessary, with its original goal of the protection of persons and their concomitant rights. The international legal community has now jettisoned this moral imperative for sovereignty,⁴⁰ and I suggest this negates the legitimacy of it for the primary reason that the march towards the protection of human rights is, taking a long view, the foundation of the idea of state sovereignty within international legal discourse.

³⁵ F.H. Hinsley, *Sovereignty* (New York: Basic Books, 1966). I also found the following research helpful in terms of the question of sovereignty and complexity. W.J. Stankiewicz, “The Validity of Sovereignty,” *In Defense of Sovereignty*, ed. W.J. Stankiewicz (London: Oxford University Press, 1969).

³⁶ Hinsley, *Sovereignty*, 1.

³⁷ Hinsley, *Sovereignty*, 25.

³⁸ Hinsley, *Sovereignty*, 26.

³⁹ Hinsley, *Sovereignty*, 233-235.

⁴⁰ According to current international law norms, states only require an *effective and independent system of government of a community within a defined territory*. Article 4 of *United Nations Charter*, Benedetto Conforti, *The Law and Practice of the United Nations*, 3rd ed. (Leiden: Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, 2005), 25.

Conclusion

19. I have cast the beginning of this research by showing that sovereignty was, for centuries past, always justified by deontological considerations. In fact, along with this fact it is interesting to note that, historically, theorists in general really tended to come out of the woodwork whenever their society or paradigm was crumbling morally and literally before their very eyes. This could be said of Plato, Aristotle, Cicero, Augustine, and most pointedly for this research, the political theorists of the cataclysmic Modern Period such as Jean Bodin and a host of others.⁴¹ Perhaps in some way these written works are in some way trying to explain the tragic events while attempting to maintain the core of their widely held beliefs which, in most cases, actually led to the catastrophes. In some sense these theorists may be unconsciously trying to account for their own commitment to these flawed world-views.

20. Given the above, I will here present my own definition of sovereignty. I come back to the statement I began with: sovereignty denotes two main tenets which support its legitimacy. First, there must be a political body or person with the capacity to exercise power over a specific community and place such that no higher authority exists within its jurisdiction. Second, sovereignty must insist that a positive moral imperative is placed on the person or body executing such power in practice. Sovereignty only really occurs when both these requirements are met, otherwise without “capacity” a population is destined to be divided and ruled by merely the strongest, which only brings us back to the experiences common in the dark chapters of human history. Without a “moral imperative,” absolute capacity puts the well being of the state at the mercy of the disposition, despotic or laudable, of those in charge: whether it is a monarch, aristocracy, oligarchy, or democracy. History is surfeited with so many examples of both outcomes it is weighed down to the point of being immovable. As N. Politis wrote from France in the early twentieth century:

In any human society, the organization of the justice system meets an essential need of realizing the satisfaction of individual and collective interests. It is the indispensable condition for the maintenance and progress of society. For in ensuring the triumph of law, it guarantees social peace. Without it, it's back to anarchy and primitive barbarism. So it is to the manner in which justice is administered in a country that is usually appreciated its degree of civilization. Where the justice was not organized, there was not strictly speaking a State.⁴²

⁴¹ C.G. Bateman, “Nicaea and Sovereignty: The Introduction of An Idea about the Beginnings of State Sovereignty,” *International Zeitschrift* 7.2 (October 2011): 58-62.

⁴² N. Politis, *La Justice Internationale* (Paris: Librairie Hachette, 1924), 7. Dans toute société humaine, l'organisation de la justice répond à un besoin primordial, c'est à savoir à la satisfaction des intérêts individuels et collectifs. Elle constitue l'indispensable condition du maintien et du progrès de la société. Car, en assurant le triomphe du droit, elle garantit la paix sociale. Sans elle, c'est le retour à l'anarchie et à la barbarie primitives. Aussi est-ce à la manière dont la justice est administrée dans un pays que l'on apprécie ordinairement son degré de civilisation. Là où la justice n'est pas organisée, il n'y a pas à proprement parler d'État.

21. Perhaps the great challenge, then, for our modern world is to admit that we have a world in which some “sovereign” states are regularly violating the human rights of their own citizens, and some who regularly abuse the rights of other nation’s citizens. Perhaps full sovereignty rights should only be accorded to a state which has met certain standards of care and capacity, at least internally. The representatives of nation states should be able to agree that beyond defined territories and populations, a sovereign state must be, in the end, one that consistently demonstrates the protection and well being of all citizens under its care. Otherwise, our definition of sovereignty in practice becomes little more than a theoretical defense of the status quo.